

LINGUISTIC STUDY OF PROVERBS ABOUT NATURAL PHENOMENA IN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: this article provides feedback on the scientific and theoretical foundations of linguistic research of proverbs related to natural phenomena in linguistics.

Keywords: Linguistics, linguistic research, folklore studies, proverbs, M.Z.Sadriddinov.

Proverbs are the embodiment of folk oral creativity, which shows the wisdom of the people, the spirit of the nation, its culture. The study, research of proverbs, in particular folk art, is becoming very important today. This "gem" was of interest not only to linguists, but also to representatives of various other spheres. For example: ethnographers, culturologists, folklorists, literary critics, linguists, psychologists, philosophers, etc. Proverbs are the experience of the people, his breath, his Assembly, his joy and joy, his sorrow and the Hunter, this is the truth of the people, the Beacon that leads him to the right path. "The people inherit the life experience they have accumulated over the centuries with the help of various means to future generations. Proverbs are such an invaluable example of inheritance. They are the Times of osha as an important source of folk wisdom, passing from mouth to mouth and polished. Proverbs, like other genres of folk oral creativity, are the National Literary and cultural wealth of each people. They fully represent the national – cultural characteristics of the people and its facets, worldview, moral norms and principles, the state of mind of the nation."¹

The history of the study of Uzbek Proverbs: both the history of the collection and study of Uzbek folk masterpieces, proverbs that are one of the popular genres of Uzbek folk art, and their use by writers and scientists in their works go back to distant times.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND REVIEW.

Interest in the proverb from the point of view of the literary language, its use to increase the artistry of the work and ensure the fluency of the artistic language were the focus of attention of all-time word artists. Yusuf Khas Khajib, Akhmad Yassavi, Rabguziy, Lutfi, Alisher Navoi, Babur, Abdulgazi Bakhadurkhan, Munis, Ogakhiy, Nadira, Mukimi, Furqat, Avaz, Khamza, Sadriddin Ayniy, Fitrat, Chulpan, Abdulla Qodiriy, Aybek. When the works of G. Gulam and many other creators are carefully studied, we see how many proverbs they contain.

In particular, the great scientist of the XI century M. Koshkhari in his work "Devonu dictionary Turk" widely used proverbs of peoples belonging to the Turkish language family. This work is not only a book that interprets the words of the language of that time alone, but also a unique philological work, which at that time also provided information about the entire Central Asian circle, that is, about the vast and large territory that stretched from the upper reaches to Movorounnakh, Khorezm, Fergana, Bukhara. Hence, this valuable scientific and rare work is also a work that combines all the achievements of folk oral creativity, especially when

¹ Samadov K. About the essence of our proverbs. - Tashkent. Culture Of Uzbekistan. 1965, 213-p.

interpreting scientific ideas that study folk Proverbs, paying great attention to folk Proverbs, collecting folk proverbs for the first time. It's about M. Koshgari himself writes: "I decorated this book with special alphabetical words, Sakhs, Proverbs, songs, literary passages called rajaz and prose." Hence, the collection and study of Uzbek folk Proverbs was given by Mahmud Koshkhari in the 11th century. His work "the Office of dictionary Turk" brings 275 Proverbs.²

DISCUSSION.

According to barley's confirmation, "the proverb cannot be considered separately from the complex of relations with other related forms like it." The reserve of Proverbs of each people is unique. Uzbek folk proverbs are a derivative of the wisdom of the Uzbek people. The question of the classification of Proverbs related to the phenomenon of nature in Uzbek Proverbs is a topic that is waiting for its solution today.

In linguistics, the scientific approach to Proverbs related to the phenomenon of nature, that is, the definition of Proverbs as stable compounds, although little, has found its reflection in the process of scientific research.

Today, economic-political, cultural and scientific relations between people, peoples, countries, international-cultural communicative processes have led to the emergence of a new sphere - linguoculturology, which has a special specific direction and subject between a number and cultural studies, such as the interaction of languages in the field of linguistics and the culture of language, as well as the National As a result, by the end of the 20th century, a new branch of linguistics, which aims to study the problem of language and culture, developed rapidly linguoculturology. Linguoculturology is a separate scientific field that jointly studies language - culture-phenomena that reflect the inextricable connection of "language and culture", its formation and development. Again, it is worth noting that proverbs that express the same meaning in two languages do not exactly coincide.

The world of Proverbs about the natural phenomenon is a "fertile field" for scientists - linguists, literary critics, paremiologists, folklorists, ethnographers, who are considered specialists in various fields, to conduct research. This is natural, since the proverb form *ihcham*, despite its simplicity, can be considered from different research points of view. Proverbs about the phenomenon of nature, as a semantic and structurally complete completed text, also attract the attention of textual linguistics, which is a rather multifaceted area of linguistics about language. Different proverbs in one language, even mutually close and not at all fraternal, can belong to a single logical type and indicate the same symptom. Therefore, they will be directly related to logical semantics and semiotics. Proverbs about a natural phenomenon are statements that are considered a certain syntactic unit from a grammatical point of view. Therefore, the formal structure of a proverb as a syntactic unit should be studied in grammar.

One of the founders of scientific paremiology is G.L. Permyakov. In his opinion, the figurative word turnover, which represents "unfinished thought", is called *matal*s, and the figurative meaning sentences that form the "finished thought" are called Proverbs. Both proverbs and sayings about the natural phenomenon G. L. Permyakov (printed mold words) considers within the framework of his theory. In the vocabulary reserve of each language there will be

² Zhurayeva B. Linguistic position and spiritual methodological application of Proverbs, abstract-Samarkand.2002, 17-18 pp.

complex specific molds (clichés), that is, stagnant, applied ready-made in speech, indivisible turnover. It can be said that proverbs are considered an object of linguoculturology.³ Linguoculturology studies the intersection point of language and culture, at the heart of which are proverbs. Proverbs reflect the historical experience of the people, their past. In terms of Proverbs, it is studied semantically in folklore and Linguistics.

Proverbs about the phenomenon of nature have been widely studied in folklore as genre texts, their study in linguistics, that is, in linguoculturology, is now being established. From the point of view of the pragmatic point of view, proverbs about a natural phenomenon can be expressed for various purposes, including such meanings as pointing, comforting, warning in a proverb. However, not every proverb will be the subject of linguoculturological research. In this case, it is necessary to study proverbs in which the Ethnos, history, culture of each people are closely related.

Proverbs about the phenomenon of nature, of course, perform a methodological task. The methodological tasks of Proverbs are constant for proverbs about a natural phenomenon, arising from their internal nature and performing a real task in any text as well. The words contained in Proverbs about the phenomenon of nature are not found in this very form at times other than the content of Proverbs. That is why it also testifies to the fact that proverbs are not just a unit of language, but a small-volume work of art, a unit of speech. Proverbs we know that they also express concepts related to era, culture. If linguoculturology studies Nature, Society, art, history and other social and cultural spheres of a person, then linguistics represents a worldview that reflects the language as linguistic models of the world linguistic landscape.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it studies the interaction of Proverbs and language about the natural phenomenon, the manifestations of folk culture, which are reflected in the impact. As the main object of Proverbs about the phenomenon of nature, “the interconnection of language and substance at the time of their entry into contact and the interpretation of this attitude in the case of one whole system, lies in the fact that society arises in the process of language communication of marriage and is based on cultural values.” In the same years, a large-scale study of the field of Proverbs about the natural phenomenon is being carried out in Uzbek dentistry. It is also on this basis that my scientific research activities are carried out.

³ Usmanova Sh. Linguoculturology. Textbook.- Tashkent, 2019. 10 p.

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